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Accelerating Progress to Local Area Energy Planning in UK Local Government

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Abstract: In an era of growing climate vulnerability, the impacts of climate change are increasingly being felt within cities and local communities. Local and regional actors have a key part to play in adaptation and mitigation – for example, the UK government estimates that up to 82% of the country’s emissions can be influenced by local authorities. However, the ability of local government to enact this influence and support community resilience to climate impacts is severely hampered by their increasingly precarious financial position and a lack of formal responsibilities and associated resources to engage with local stakeholders.

This paper examines the role of local government in accelerating the transition to net zero in the UK. We present the results of a risk analysis of 13 Local Area Energy Planning (LAEP) documents from 7 separate local authorities in the UK, as well as a mapping of practical implications from 6 “trailblazer” local authorities in England and the actions they are taking to deliver projects identified under their LAEPs.

This research highlights challenges with the national policy framework’s approach of considering local authorities as key change agents in the net zero space. We examine the tensions between the technical potentials of Local Area Energy Planning and the socio-technical system of local authority governance, including political, financial and social factors. We find that to be effective change agents, the lack of devolved powers to enact legislation or regulate is not the key constraint; rather, they are challenged in terms of their capacity to develop and implement technical projects, convene networks of diverse stakeholders for place-based approaches, and drive change at an accelerated pace locally.

Finally, we recommended enhanced governance approaches to reduce non-technical barriers to implementation, and consider the needs of diverse stakeholders for equitable, inclusive climate action.

Keywords: net zero, United Kingdom, local area energy planning, local government, resilience

Main highlights:

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- Local authorities are expected to take key roles in net zero and resilience
- Local authorities lack capacity (human, institutional and financial)
- The national policy framework for net zero is underdeveloped
- There are multiple unaddressed risks to implementing net zero projects
- LAEP is a useful methodology, but moving to implementation and delivery is challenging

Abbreviations

Use a two-column table to explain the abbreviations.

LAEP	Local Area Energy Plan
UK	United Kingdom
RAG	Red-Amber-Green
BEIS	Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy
ESC	Energy Systems Catapult
SME	Small-and-Medium Enterprise
PPP	Public-Private Partnership

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Introduction

The United Kingdom has committed to achieve net zero emissions in the UK economy by 2050, through legally-binding targets signed in 2019 (UK Government, 2019), seeking to address increasing risks such as extreme weather events and related impacts to citizens (Burnett 2025, Climate Change Committee 2025).

The UK government envisages local authorities as being critical actors in achieving net zero, and place-based action has become more prominent in the academic literature on net zero in recent years. However, there remains uncertainty in the literature about the scale of emissions that local governments can affect. UK100, a net zero local government network, suggests that roughly 4% to 9% of scope 1 and 2 emissions can be influenced by local government, with uncertainty around scope 3 emissions. However, the current Net Zero Strategy from the BEIS suggests that local UK authorities influence 82%, a stark difference.

Local governments have a variety of roles to play in the governance of net zero adaptation, covering strategic planning, regulation creation and enforcement, coordination and collaboration of stakeholders, and acting as the accountable governance body. However, as yet, local governments do not have a statutory responsibility to make progress towards net zero (LGA, 2025).

In terms of strategic planning, Den Uyl & Russell (2017) suggest that local governments are well-placed to act as accountable bodies for owning the responsibility for net zero adaptation. LGA (2025) recommends clarity in roles and responsibilities for stakeholders in local governance systems, and clear chains of accountability. Poulter & Bolton (2021) recommend clarity in local regulatory frameworks to avoid “gaming” of systems and enforce regulations. Busch et al (2021) find that co-creation of energy sector regulatory frameworks with the regulated actors ensures salience.

A barrier to greater strategic planning is devolution: Sugar & Webb (2022) suggest that local governments have limited powers in the net zero space, and further devolution of powers would enable greater net zero adaptation. The 2024 English Devolution White Paper (Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2024) suggests that new Strategic Authorities will be the responsible bodies for net zero, supporting this assertion.

Bedford, Catney & Robinson (2023) highlight that local and regional government silo their expertise, lacking collaboration with the “limited ability to integrate policies locally” as a key barrier. This is supported by Berthod et al (2022) discussing collaborative and implementation structures and required power-sharing among partners. Linton, Clarke & Tozer (2020) further recommend local governments as facilitators for deep decarbonisation projects. Carr-Whitworth et al (2023) suggest clear governance structures for net zero as a key enabler. Tingey & Webb (2020) also discuss devolution of responsibilities, and the need for responsible parties at a local level for implementing community climate resilience.

Place-based approaches are seen as key, and a core tenet of these is participation from local communities, private sector organisations, third-sector groups and governance bodies such as local and regional government (Bouw et al 2022, Berthod et al 2022). Local Area Energy

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Planning (LAEP) is recommended by the UK government as a place-based approach to net zero adaptation planning (Collins & Walker 2023, Energy Systems Catapult 2025). Bouw et al (2022) further address neighbourhood energy planning, and the justice issues inherent in selecting community participants in planning, given wealthier areas may have more capacity for participation than poorer ones.

This article presents the results of a risk analysis of 13 Local Area Energy Planning (LAEP) documents from 7 separate local authorities in the UK, as well as a mapping of practical implications from 6 “trailblazer” local authorities in England and the delivery actions they are taking. We are defining “risk” here as the risk of not delivering energy and sustainability projects identified under a LAEP. LAEP is a methodology for producing place-based net zero action plans with robust, quantitative modelling of geographically-bounded energy systems, and this article elaborates the progress towards delivery of projects identified using LAEP data, the risks to delivery seen in current LAEP documents, and the governance and policy considerations required for effective delivery pipelines for net zero projects in local governments.

Methodology

In total, 13 local authority reports from seven different authorities at Unitary, County and Combined authority scales were examined. The documents analysed are outlined in Table 1:

Table 1: Local Authority Documents Analysed

<u>Local Authority</u>	<u>Document</u>	<u>Description</u>
Greater Manchester Combined Authority	Local Area Energy Plan Outline Business Case (28th July 2023)	Post-LAEP framework development document, based on the Tameside GMC LAEP of June 2022
Greater Manchester Combined Authority	Local Area Energy Plan - Progress update (20th July 2023)	Overview of the LAEP to Environment, Climate Change and Neighbourhoods Scrutiny Committee
Greater Manchester Combined Authority	Local Area Energy Plan: Appendix 1 Monitoring Report (20th July 2023)	Focus on Manchester City actions to date and progress towards the 2038 Net Zero target
Greater Manchester Combined Authority	Local Area Energy Plan: Appendix 2 Action Plan Matrix (20th July 2023)	Layout of topic, actions, deadlines, and achievements RAG (Red, Amber, Green) status and future priorities
Newcastle City Council	SSH Phase 2 - D39 Smart Energy Plan - Newcastle City Council (2018 Energy Systems Catapult)	Phase 2 update plan from Newcastle County Council on trailblazer LAEP projects
Newcastle City Council	SSH WP2 Newcastle Local Area Energy Strategy - NCC Local area energy planning	Modelling report from Energy Systems Catapult: high level outlook and timeline for technological based changes

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	evidence base (2018 Energy Systems Catapult)	
Bristol City Council	Bristol City LEAP 2025/5 five-year business plan	Executive summary of the five-year business plan for Bristol City LAEP. Full document not available.
Bristol City Council	Bristol Net Zero by 2030: the evidence base (Centre for Sustainable Energy (Dec 2019))	Feeder document for Bristol City LEAP development
Bridgend County Borough Council	Bridgend County Borough Council LAEP Report to Cabinet (Jan 2022)	Support and presentation document for approval of Bridgend LAEP refresh
Bridgend County Borough Council	Bridgend County Borough Council - D37/38: Smart Energy Plan SSH Phase 2 (Jan 2019)	BEIS and ESC document to describe a roadmap of projects and activities to enable BCBC to decarbonise heat within the wider energy system.
West Yorkshire Combined Authority	West Yorkshire Combined Authority - Project Approvals - LAEP - Investment Priority 4	Report on the progress of and funding for Investment Priority 4 - Tackling the climate emergency and Env Sust Investment
Calderdale Council	Calderdale (Yorkshire) Climate Action Plan 23-26	Climate change action plan for Calderdale for stakeholder engagement, referring to LAEP priorities
City of York Council	City of York LAEP for York Council by ESC	Local Area Energy Plan for the City of York

These documents were then critically assessed through a risk analysis with a governance lens for delivering LAEP activities. In total, 80 individual risks were identified from the text of the reports. These risks were categorised on a five-point Red-Amber-Green (RAG) scale, with a score of 5 (red) being a severe risk, and a 1 (green) being a minimal, but present, risk. Following this, using a deductive thematic analysis coding process (Braun & Clarke, 2006), these risks were coded into 9 separate categories, and scores assigned to each category based on the average RAG rating achieved in that category, to determine the average severity of risk seen in each area.

These documents, however, did not provide a clear picture of on-the-ground delivery of projects related to LAEPs, and as such, a primary research exercise was undertaken to fill in these gaps. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with Council Officers due to their active role, consultants to the Local Authorities, as well as external funding bodies and Authority-linked delivery bodies, such as One-Stop-Shops, and national bodies such as the National Wealth Fund. From the 21 interviews conducted (covering 12 Council Officers, 5 Consultants, 2 Funders and 2 SMEs), a purposive sub-sample of 6 was selected for in-depth

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thematic analysis. This sub-sample was chosen because these interviews provided the richest and most detailed accounts of project delivery challenges and innovations.

These interviews were then thematically analysed, creating 5 broader themes of Leadership, Delivery Plans, Engagement, Finance & Human Resources (capital). The frequency was recorded than analysed by groups of Authority types: Unitary Authorities, Combined Authorities and Districts (within counties). As frequency of responses does not denote the importance of an action in thematic analysis, a latent analysis was undertaken to identify any significant underlying trends or causes of any barriers noted or actions taken.

Results

Risk Analysis

The risk analysis outputs for the 13 local authority documents are presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Distribution of codes for risk categories and RAG rating

<u>Risk Category</u>	<u>Number of 5 (Red) Risks</u>	<u>Number of Overall Risks</u>	<u>Average RAG Rating Achieved</u>
Regulation		10	3.4
Funding	1	14	3.2
Leadership		11	2.9
Engagement		10	2.8
Supply Chains	1	8	2.8
Policy		10	2.7
Technical	2	23	2.6
Economic		4	2.3
Other	2	2	5

From this analysis, we can see that regulation and funding are the most critical risks to LAEP governance, except for “Other” risks. Crucially, the highest average risk rating was found in the 'Other' category. These were risks not explicitly identified within the LAEP documents themselves but noted by the researchers as critical omissions: the phenomenon of 'comfort-taking' which is a rebound effect (BEIS, 2023), and the failure to account for regional carbon intensities of electricity.

Thematic Analysis

From the results of the thematic analysis of six semi-structured interviews with local authority officers and related staff, five innovation categories were identified: Delivery Plan (16), Leadership (12), Engagement (9), Finance (6) and Human Resources (5)

Figure 1 presents a comparison of innovation area frequency by local authority type:

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Figure 1: Frequency of innovation by local authority type

Unitary Authority analysis			Combined Authority analysis		
Innovation category	Frequency		Innovation category	Frequency	
Leadership	5	24%	Leadership	3	27%
Delivery plan	6	29%	Delivery plan	4	36%
Engagement	4	19%	Engagement	2	18%
Finance	3	14%	Finance	1	9%
Human resources	3	14%	Human resources	1	9%
	21	100%		11	100%

District analysis - County Councils			Meta		
Innovation category	Frequency		Innovation category	Frequency	
Leadership	4	25%	Leadership	12	25%
Delivery plan	6	38%	Delivery plan	16	33%
Engagement	3	19%	Engagement	9	19%
Finance	2	13%	Finance	6	13%
Human resources	1	6%	Human resources	5	10%
	16	100%		48	100%

To help understand this, a mapping exercise was undertaken to establish the links between the 5 areas of innovation and their strength of influence. A relationship diagram was produced to map the interactions between these five areas, and how strongly these areas influence each other.

Figure 2 - Relationship diagram of LAEP innovation categories

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The numbers inside the innovation areas shown in Figure 2 reflects their ranking in terms of number of mentions, from most (#1) to least (#5); the influence level is indicated by the weight of the joining arrows.

Notably, the mapping exercise reveals that while Finance is a critical component, it is not directly influenced by Leadership in this context. Instead, its influence is mediated through Delivery Plans and Human Resources, suggesting that financial leverage is contingent on operational capacity and strategic planning. Finance also did not directly connect to Leadership in the sense that no Authority was seeking to use its own funds directly, although some may leverage their asset bases through Public Private Partnerships or indirect, low risk methods. However, it is clear that leadership could influence potential delivery partners, which in turn would impact finance.

A commonly stated challenge in the interviews was a lack of human capital within Local Authorities, this having been eroded over the last decade and not replaced – or if replaced, not at the same pay scale nor seniority level. This was commented to have led to a loss of skills and experience in the role, with roles often being added to the side of an existing position; for example, Planning Officers now becoming Energy Policy Officers.

Latent analysis of the interviews, when overlaid onto the mapping exercise, showed that although human capital and resources were consistently one of the most common concerns, it ranked as the least innovated area.

Discussion

For the semi-structured interview analysis, innovation area frequency varied by type of authority – as shown in Figure 1. Whilst broadly similar to each other one variance stood out: human resources innovation in Unitary Authorities. This may be the result of a confluence of capability, opportunity and motivation, as they are a single actor and do not require multiple agencies or Districts to come together to enact change. As a Unitary Authority, they have

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higher density of coalesced staff in one place to facilitate innovation within the area of human resources. This finding suggests a critical policy lesson: structural governance arrangements have a direct impact on an authority's adaptive capacity. The coalesced structure of Unitary Authorities appears to foster the internal conditions necessary for innovation in human capital, a key enabler for all other aspects of LAEP delivery.

However, this is not to say that Unitary Authorities will have the most success in enacting a LAEP, but enabling conditions are in place. It is likely that as the recommendations of the (English) Devolution White Paper come into effect this capability will become more realised, as Districts coalesce and larger Authority/ies are created. This includes access to sufficient funding, to be able to group together enough projects to attract PPPs, the associated finance, and enough staff in one place to create a coherent and dedicated team. Human resources should be a key area of focus, as it will act as the facilitator to the others. One example of a potential impact is consideration that the high-risk ratings for 'Regulation' and 'Funding' from the document analysis (Table 2) are reflected and explained in the interview data. For example, the interviewees' comments on the lack of human capital and the erosion of skills directly speak to the 'Funding' risk. The challenges of navigating different agencies and the absence of a clear national framework speak to the 'Regulation' risk. With a big enough “in-house” team to resource these areas then delivery will be perceived as less complex.

Whilst this work was based on a reasonable sample size, other Authorities of interest were contacted for interview but never responded. Furthermore, due to the fact that Innovate UK funding existed for specific projects, there is a risk of an availability cascade being created leading to a bias in actions by certain Authorities. This is why two Authorities were represented per type, however, a larger sample size may even out these inherent biases. This is not to say that these innovative actions are not of benefit for replication, but they should not be considered as being all that there is. There was a clear dependence noted by Authorities on having to wait for grant funding rounds before they felt they could take a next step in research or action. For example, the wider Greater Manchester Combined Authority LAEP is estimated at circa £19B, but they only allocated £1m of ringfenced business rates income towards the LAEP for the 24/25 budget period. This is a clear blocker to action, and if financial feasibility is presently limited, then there should be a wider future readiness program established.

As a brief example, we may consider what does a key proposed staff role look like, that may address the problems highlighted under human resources in Table 3. This role would be one of an educated, qualified and experienced “Green Champion” who can act as a collator of information, convener of like-minded people and an educator for other Officers, Elected Members and external actors alike. They would need to be appropriately resourced with a senior level job role, or at the very least ensured access to the Executive level, and embedded within any new delivery teams for the LAEP.

A key role would be to create/collate/deliver supporting information packs based on the overall delivery model, tailored to specific audiences. These may mean specific foci such as PPP, finance partners, community engagement work (SME & citizens) and the needs of both internal Officers & Elected Members. In addition to this there will be a need to support the varying actors as they find and take their roles in the delivery models as mentioned. Through delivery of the appropriate guidance, information packs and support, offering appropriate

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explanation, education and networking as needed, the role will increase the speed of delivery and improve the system's resilience.

Conclusion

Achieving net zero in the UK will be a multi-scalar process, with stakeholders at national, regional and local levels needing to contribute through robust governance arrangements to achieving net zero objectives. Governance needs to consider not only planning and internal working processes, but delivery mechanisms, financing, partnership models and a wide variety of other factors for a successful net zero transition. Local governments in the UK face a number of barriers in fulfilling the governance roles they are most suited to: the absence of a salient national policy framework, the challenges of local skills and delivery capabilities, the fragmented and short-term funding structure for local authorities. Addressing these issues will both accelerate the first stages of a LAEP delivery and increase the future readiness of English local authorities. Some actions are already within the capability of the present power structures, but it is predicted that with the proposed devolution and aggregation of powers/assets/staffing there will be greater opportunities to move further, faster and with greater efficacy. Ultimately, this research demonstrates that LAEPs cannot succeed as purely technical documents parachuted into a dysfunctional system. Accelerating progress to net zero requires a co-designed approach where national government empowers local authorities. Not just with plans, but with the sustained resources, capacity, and convening authority to turn them into a reality.

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